

FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL ETHICS OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article presents the history of pedagogical ethics, information on improving the pedagogical skills and pedagogical ethics of future elementary school teachers.

Key words: Professional skills, knowledge, skills, competence, talent, factors, communication, pedagogue.

Sudden changes taking place in society, various problems related to human education are also reflected in the pedagogical process. Socio-economic relations, intense competition in the market economy has an impact on "teacher-pupil" and "teacher-student" relations. Only as a result of learning, humanity acquires creativity in the field of work and creativity, work based on social and moral standards, and the ability to communicate with other people through personal relationships. English scientist Dj. Simon called knowledge "a way of forming a person for society." The famous Russian writer and publicist N. G. Chernyshevsky in his works emphasizes that knowledge includes three perfect components: comprehensive knowledge, knowledge that invites thinking, knowledge that develops noble feelings. Knowledge is conveyed to the mind and thinking of the young generation only due to the high professional skills of the teacher. However, at the same time, the teacher must have high humanity and ethics. Pedagogical scientist M.A. Verb says that pedagogical ethics is an important basis of a teacher's professional culture. It is known that ethics (Greek ethos - character, custom) is the science of norms and rules of behavior, human interaction. Pedagogical ethics, based on the standards of universal ethics,

determines the normative and moral positions that the future teacher should follow in the process of communication with people in his environment, colleagues, students, and their parents. In humanitarian pedagogy, for centuries, its best representatives have been saying that ardent love for children is the starting point of ethical standards. In this, the emotional and value relations towards the child are manifested in different ways. The main pedagogical idea of scientists such as J.J.Russo, L.N.Tolstoy, R.Steiner was to love children and give them as much creative freedom as possible in accordance with the needs of communication depending on their age. Scientists such as I.G.Pestalotti and Ya.Korchak confidently emphasized that it is necessary not only to love children, but also to share their joys and sorrows. R. Owen and A.S. Makarenko, taking care of their students, taught them to live happily in the future life. In the science of pedagogy, some scientists have emphasized in their research that they are in favor of the strictness of the teacher towards children. However, no matter what scientists say about harshness and rudeness, it is still impossible to achieve spiritual harmony between teachers and students without feelings of close relationship with children, politeness, sincere understanding of each other, and caring. V. A. Sukhomlinsky rightly called it the alpha and omega of the educational process. Ya. A. Komensky believed that all institutions where children receive education in the last periods of the Middle Ages should be like "workshops that glorify humanity". Later, famous scientists such as I.I. Betskoi, N.I. Pirogov, P.P. Blonsky, M. Montessori also wrote about it in their works. Humanitarian feelings towards children, that is, to be kind and caring, to understand and take care of them from the heart, are especially extremely relevant in the process of today's global changes, science and technology, computer and modern information and communication technologies.

The humanity of a primary school teacher is reflected in the Law "On

Education", in the reforms carried out in the field of education in our country, and in the observance of the rules on their rights and freedoms, which are defined in various documents on education and protection of children accepted at

the international level. The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (November 20, 1989) states that every child has the right to complete education, to engage in arts and sports, and to have a free and personal opinion. Russian pedagogue Ya. Korchak in his "Regulations of the Children's Home" listed the rights of children to play, to keep secrets, to be attentive to their problems, to be demanding, to protest, and the rights of the child to think freely. It is emphasized that coercive actions against children, that is, suppressing someone's opinion, destroying their pride, using corporal punishment, restricting their freedom, and depriving them of food and sleep are not allowed. These norms apply equally to social and family education. The spectrum of ethical qualities of a teacher, which is manifested in his interactions with his students in class and outside of class, is extremely wide and diverse. Special research conducted in pedagogy on this issue shows that primary school students in educational institutions appreciate the sincerity, politeness, kindness, fairness of their teachers, helping students to understand some problems related to the subject being studied, the desire to help them understand the material given in the lesson, kindness, they appreciate honesty, hard work, restraint and calmness, recognition of the student's ability to know and curiosity, patience, demandingness and a number of other qualities of pedagogical professional importance. However, students mostly value sincerity, honesty, and sincerity in their relationship with the teacher. The well-known scientist M. O. Knebel stated that the science of pedagogy requires qualities that are close to the mother's qualities in relation to the child. In his book "Pedagogy of Poetry" ("Pedagogical Poem"), he wrote about the need for a teacher to give his heart to his young students, just as a mother gives her children the best virtues she

has. This is the main content of the teaching profession. Giving your heart to children is both difficult and joyful. Therefore, it is difficult because it requires not only mental but also physical effort. That's why, happily, the answer to all the efforts, difficulties and hardships of the teacher flows back to him like the energy of youth. In order to ensure the mutuality of pedagogical requirements in the family and in various educational institutions for the formation of a student as a person, a young teacher and educator should choose reliable and tested methods of communication. Each teacher has an informal "code of ethics" that he strictly adheres to in his interactions with colleagues in his pedagogical team. What can a teacher who has graduated from a higher pedagogical educational institution and joined the pedagogical team as a young specialist start his career? This difficult question is sure to put all young teachers in an exciting position.

We ask you to adhere to the following recommendations using the teachings of master teachers with many years of experience:

1. Don't be in a hurry to criticize the traditions and work process that have been polished over the years in the educational institution and propose new rules that you like "right out the door". Try to understand the situation in the team, the successes and failures of your colleagues, representatives of different generations.

2. When discussing a co-teacher's open class or teaching style, especially in the presence of leaders, start by talking about his achievements and positive aspects. With this, you will help your colleague morally.

3. It is not polite to blame the group of students, the head of the class, and the parents if the students cannot complete the assigned tasks or behave undisciplined in the class where you directly teach. The reasons for failure should be found in your methodological mistakes in your professional activity.

4. If you do not agree with the comments and objections of your senior,

respected colleague or institution's administration regarding your pedagogical activity, you should not take a position of compromise, but you should not strain the relationship either. It is best to provide evidence that strengthens your position and try to prove your opponents wrong.

5. Remember: your benevolence, enterprisingness, politeness, desire for mutual cooperation at work, willingness to recognize the best experience, support a new initiative - create a favorable environment for successful activities and are the main factor in the emergence of a good creative mood in the work team. Therefore, pedagogical ethics is an important part of pedagogical skills. It should be remembered that the effectiveness of mutual relations (teacher - student) often depends on the observance of pedagogical tact. References:

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